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EVALUATING THE INTELLECTUAL ABILITY OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP SUBJECTS AND MANAGERS IN MARKET CONDITIONS

ОЦЕНКА ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОЙ СПОСОБНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ И МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНКА

©Ibragimov I.,

Tashkent State University of Economics,

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

©Ибрагимов И. У.,

Ташкентский государственный экономический университет,

Ташкент, Узбекистан

Abstract. The article provides an overview of the current methods for evaluating the intellectual capital of the organization, analyzes techniques that allow to assess both the intellectual capital in general and its individual components. The author proves that entrepreneurship currently occupies an important niche in the economy of the state. But the insufficient elaboration of questions in science about the psychological characteristics of entrepreneurs, the fragmented and multifaceted information predetermine the directions in the study of this issue. The problem of studying the psychological characteristics of the entrepreneur is relevant for the present time. In general, the author developed a methodology for assessing the intellectual ability of entrepreneurs.

Аннотация. В статье приводится обзор актуальных методик оценки интеллектуального капитала организации, проанализированы методики, позволяющие оценить как интеллектуальный капитал в целом, так и отдельные его составляющие. Автор доказывает, что предпринимательство в настоящее время занимает важную нишу в экономике государства. Но недостаточная разработанность вопросов в науке о психологических особенностях предпринимателей, разрозненность и многоплановость информации предопределяют направления в изучении данного вопроса. Проблема изучения психологических особенностей предпринимателя является актуальной для настоящего времени. В целом, автором разработана методика оценки интеллектуальных способностей предпринимателей.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, intellectual abilities, valuation, intellectual capital, intangible assets, evaluation of intellectual ability.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, интеллектуальные способности, оценка, интеллектуальный капитал, нематериальные активы, оценка интеллектуальной способности.

Introduction

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a leading industrial country in Central Asia. The distinctive features of the country are highly developed automobile, airplane and machine building, metallurgy, natural gas and oil processing, chemical, textiles, food processing and other industries.

As a result of the economic policy carried out for developing the small business and entrepreneurship in our republic this branch of economy is developing notably. For this, special

system of laws, controlling documents, especially, normative-legal standards worked out according to the governmental program is serving as a fundamental document (www.stat.uz).

As a result the number of objects of the small business and entrepreneurship is increasing in the region. In particular, the beneficial conditions for developing this sphere and number of decrees and decisions adopted by our president and the government is positively influencing for the development of the sphere.

“It is needed to note that the works implemented for the strengthening the conditions of entrepreneurship is noted in the ratings of the international economic organizations. The World Bank has announced the rating of “conducting business”. Uzbekistan has shown the result of rising for sixteen steps up in a single year and occupied eighty seventh place.

Discussion results

At the end of 2017, more than 38,100 newly created small business entities were operating in Uzbekistan, which is 22 percent more than in 2016.

In the structure of operating small business entities, small enterprises account for 8.2 percent (18,900 units), and micro-firms account for 91.8 percent.

This is while 20.2 percent or 2,354 family enterprises are operating in the sphere of accommodation and food services, 15.4 percent or 1,803 family enterprises are operating in the trade sphere, 12 percent or 1,401 enterprises — in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, 1.3 percent or 149 enterprises — in information and communication, 1.2 percent or 143 enterprises — in construction, 1.1 percent or 133 enterprises — in transportation and storage sphere.

I'd like specially note that as a result of our reforms carried out in our republic the contribution of small business and private entrepreneurship to the GDP has risen from 31 percent of 2000 to 56, 7 percent at present Now this branch of our economy is producing one of three parts of industrial products, ninety eight percent of agricultural products.

More than seventy seven percent of our employed people, pay attention to this, are working in this branch and feeding their families, contributing to the wealth, If I say that first of all, this is in support of the possibility opened by the independence of our country, I am not mistaken.”

The gross domestic product of our country has risen 8,1 percent, industrial product producing 8,3 percent, capital constructing 10,9 percent, retail turnover 14,3 percent. Constituent of about seventy percent of the whole produced product is readymade surplus value products.

Namangan region has achieved the rise of importance and small business contribution to the regional economy year by year as a result of implementation of work for its development and supporting entrepreneurship. If in 2014 the contribution of small business subjects to the regional GDP was 79,7 percent, in 2015 this performance has reached to 80,2 percent. This index was 79, 5 by the end of 2013. There were registered 15122 small business subjects in January of 2015 and this was higher for 104, 7 percent in comparison to the January of 2014.

In particular, if to analyze the contribution of small business subjects to the branches of economy it was 48,8 percent in 2013, and this was risen 0,7 points and it was 49,5 percent at the end of 2014. In the districts the highest was in Chortoq district (90,4%) and the lowest was in Mingbuloq district (13,2%) at the end of 2014. If analyze the contribution of small business subjects' contribution to the agricultural branches it was 99, 1% (it had risen to one point in comparison to the same period of the previous year), in construction work 87, 9% (+0, 1 point), retailing 45, 7% (+0, 9 points), totally in services 63, 2% (+0, 8 points).

Goods exported by small business subjects has increased 115,6% in comparison to the same period of the last year and made 56,1 million dollars at the end of 2015. As a result of contribution of small businesses to the regional export has increased from 48,1% to 60,3% accordingly.

In achieving these results family businesses also contributed notably as our government has paid attention to as well as to the other branches and spheres of economy. Familial business has also made an important contribution to employment of temporarily unemployed part of the population as it has contributed to increasing consumption goods, and rising of the size of GDP.

The economic potential of the small entrepreneurship is considered by its intellectual, wealth and financial capability and it runs by the aimed plan of development and by supplying strong enough capital against the economic unbalances. An offer for evaluating the intellectual ability of small entrepreneurship was made as a system of local indexes.

For local system of evaluating the intellectual ability of entrepreneurship the following system is offered

Table

LOCAL SYSTEM OF EVALUATING THE INTELLECTUAL ABILITY OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP SUBJECTS

<i>consistent</i>	<i>Human capital</i>	<i>System capital</i>	<i>Customer capital</i>
Innovations	1. K ₁ – Takes into account the professional education level of personnel 2. K ₂ – Takes into account the part of expenses for educating and retraining the personnel	1. K ₆ – Takes into account the investment into new informational technologies	1. K ₈ – Takes into account the segmentation of branch market
Effectiveness	1. K ₃ – Takes into account the amount of surplus value of per personnel. 2. K ₄ – Takes into account the value of pre income tax of per personnel		1. K ₉ – Takes into account the income per personnel
Stability	1. K ₅ – Takes into account the fluctuation of leading specialists	1. K ₇ – Takes into account the contribution of new personnel	1. K ₁₀ – Takes into account the frequency of orders

Source: the table is prepared by the author.

Integration of local system of evaluating the intellectual ability of entrepreneurship subjects will provide us with the index of intellectual ability and its calculation was made by the following algorithm:

$$IInP = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^2)}, \tag{1}$$

x_i is a former of intellectual ability here and — (K₁-K₁₀) are the components.

Entrepreneurship activity is widely developed under the market economy. And its development and perfection is connected to widening of its essence and broadening the tasks. These tasks can be divided into the following types:

- application of the local system of intellectual ability evaluation of small business;

- material resource tasks, that is, every entrepreneurship activity must be supplied with needed objective sources of raw material, production producing sources and workforce,

-The task of organizer is that raw materials, production producing resources and workforce should be organized so that as a result entrepreneur must achieve the condition of producing the planned amount of production and get the planned amount of profit;

-The task of creativity is mainly creative relations towards to create needed product producing resources, rising the quality of production, decreasing production expenses are main reasons of rising the profit.

Fruitful fulfilling the above mentioned tasks contribute to entrepreneurship development in regions.

At the present stage of development of social production, constant development of adequate systems of motivation is required at each specific enterprise, taking into account the specific economic, political and social factors of the development of the state. Conducting research on labor motivation is necessary to ensure the effective functioning of the organization in all the variety of manifestations of both intra-firm and external forms of relations. The prevailing norms of justice in society are directly reflected in the creation of the structure of the system of motivation in a particular enterprise. Relations in the field of personnel management should be formed taking into account the objectives of all interested groups involved in the production process. The removal of the contradiction between public and individual needs in the process of production of goods and services is reflected in the organizational relations. As a result, production indicators reflect the effectiveness of the structure of the system of motivation and existing relationships. The effectiveness of leadership activities depends largely on the authority of the manager. The authority of the head of the labor collective has two sources:

- 1) personal, expressed in the leader's ability to lead influence;
- 2) public, expressed in the possession of the head of power and official prestige.

Therefore, authority is the personal influence of a person on the collective, which he acquires through his work, professional knowledge, organizational abilities, innovations, ability to work with people. With a good authoritative leader, the work performed becomes more interesting, the results achieved reinforce the sense of professional pride and commitment.

Figure. Methods for assessing the business qualities and performance of specialists and managers

The main criterion for assessing the effectiveness of the manager's work are the results of the work of the collective as a whole and of each member individually. They are measured by various production and economic indicators, which are affected by technical, economic and organizational solutions. The effectiveness of managerial decisions is to build a positive attitude of employees to work, cause team solidarity, increase job satisfaction, improve the socio-psychological climate. The result of the manager's efficiency is the production, economic and socio-psychological indicators of the company's economic activities. There are the following socio-psychological indicators: the coincidence of a formal and informal leader; a measure of cohesion (reciprocity coefficient, conflict rate, neutrality coefficient); indicator of psychological climate, etc.

Conclusions

A significant part of the early ideas about methods of measurement appeared in the late 80's. the last century, so it is not surprising that the latter are based on approaches whose roots go back to the industrial age. The scope of many methods is determined by the indicators used in them. Many of these indicators are similar to those used to measure output or product quality. As a consequence, most of these techniques provide management tools rather than providing information that may be of interest to investors. To the greatest extent, both these seemingly different purposes are combined by the Skandia Navigator and the Intangible Assets Monitor Celemi.

For all types of activities covered by the concept of "intellectual capital", it is considered the main, and it is not accidental, because the human factor is of particular importance for any company. After all, ideas arise from people, move with them, and when people go home or find another job, they take their ideas with them. Thus, the human aspect serves as a link between the four others, and around it all the Scandia discussions about intellectual capital revolve.

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